

VISCOSE RAYON FIBRES: A POTENTIAL ADDITION TO THE TECHNICAL FIBRES FAMILY?

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ABSTRACT

Natural fibres have a plethora of interesting properties that make them suitable for a wide range of applications. In addition to some particular property (e.g. mechanical or thermal capacity), the ability to manufacture a product of comparatively low or even negative carbon footprint is frequently an important consideration. In some cases this claim requires close scrutiny due to the level of wastage in the crop, where fibres are derived from food-stuffs or where there is a need to use aggressive chemical treatments.

Compared to the large body of work which has sought to use natural fibres either in a relatively raw state, or with simple processing to achieve yarns akin to wool and other materials for traditional textiles, this paper presents work on a fibre more analogous to technical fibres. Specifically, initial results from the manufacture of fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites using commercially available resin systems are discussed.

The fibre is a commercially available viscose rayon of similar dimensions to E-glass and in a continuous form. Whilst there are significant inputs in terms of the mechanical work and chemical treatments that are applied to biomass in order to produce the fibre, the fibre has the potential to produce composite laminates with higher fibre volume fractions and can be adopted easily into current fibre processes that utilise continuous synthetic fibres.

Whilst the stiffness of the fibre is comparatively low (compared with carbon or glass) the strain to failure is much higher, which requires the use of a resin system with a similar strain to failure. Two such resin systems are considered (with and without the use of a coupling agent). Data are presented for the mechanical properties of the resultant composite materials. Whilst the properties are comparatively modest compared to glass and carbon based systems, they are potentially useful. Further, it is noted that the composite has the ability to recover, to some extent, from plastic yielding.

1 INTRODUCTION

‘Green’ composite materials are of great interest in a number of sectors, particularly automotive and construction, but there is a growing interest elsewhere including the aerospace sector (although this is currently limited to ancillary equipment such as trolleys). In the majority of cases, no matter how good the ‘green’ credentials of the material, the consumer will be seeking a product that is not more expensive than the existing option and is not more expensive in the use phase. Given that natural fibres are less dense than advanced fibres this is usually achievable, although frequently the mechanical properties mean that more material may be required. The bottom line, therefore, is that for a ‘green’ composite to be classed as a sustainable alternative, the entire lifetime (manufacture, use, disposal/end-of-life) needs to be considered.

The term natural fibre encompasses a great many possibilities including plant, animal and mineral. In the current context, the focus will be on plant fibres, see e.g. [1]. The perception is frequently that natural = green = sustainable, but given the processes required to cultivate, harvest, extract and manipulate these fibres, natural fibres for composites might not be deemed a sustainable option once these economic, energy and environmental costs are taken into account.

Given the interest in natural fibre composites, it is not surprising that they are transitioning from non-structural to semi-structural roles. Nevertheless, there remain some issues, including the lower than expected mechanical performance [2] and the highly hydrophilic nature of the fibre [3]. It has been demonstrated that optimising the resin/fibre interface is one method that has the potential to improve the final composite performance. This can be achieved through physical [4-10] or chemical [11-15] treatments of the fibre and by matrix modification [16]. These optimisations can be expensive, which has the potential to reduce their industrial viability (as well as having a negative environmental impact).

However, there is an alternative. There is a great deal of interest in the use of natural fibres as a feedstock for chemicals, with, for example, certified aviation grade kerosene being produced from plant matter. The problem with this is that it is necessary to break this matter down to very simple, small molecules before further processing them into the desired form. Instead, it may be a more sustainable use of this matter to identify large molecules that can be extracted for specific applications. This is already occurring to some extent with the extraction of cellulose and the manufacture of viscose rayon (cellulose) continuous fibres. Currently, the production of this material employs significant mechanical and chemical processes, but there are a number of investigations underway that are attempting to achieve the same end result but in more environmentally friendly ways.

Owing to the good mechanical properties of Cordenka viscose rayon, one of the main applications of this fibre is in conjunction with a rubber matrix for the production of 'run-flat' tyres [17-18]. As the aspect ratio of viscose rayon is greater than the natural fibres, the interface strength is not as much of a concern as in the case of short natural fibre/rubber composites.

Short fibre cordenka viscose rayon has been used to reinforce polypropylene [19-21] and PLA [22]. These 'semi-synthetic' fibres, which do not have the inherent variability present in natural fibres, have demonstrated greater performance than E-glass composites in some instances. The short fibre Cordenka/PP and Cordenka/PLA composites achieved greater stiffness, strength and Charpy impact strength (notched and unnotched) than E-glass/PP composites. As semi-synthetic fibres are highly processed (high inputs of energy and resources), they could be environmentally worse than E-glass when a life cycle assessment is conducted to compare these different fibre systems. Owing to the reproducibility of the fibre, this type of reinforcement may be useful for engineering composites (structural components). As a result, the mechanical properties of composites with this type of fibre will be analysed. It will also be interesting to observe if the non-linear elastic behaviour of this fibre is observed within composites. This could lead to composites with high energy absorbing characteristics.

The present work is part of a wider study concerned with developing sustainable composites for engineering applications. Previous work has considered textiles produced from hemp, the need for a coupling agent to improve mechanical performance and the possibility of improving the sustainability of resin systems [23-26]. Here, viscose rayon fibres, which are commercially available from another application, have been combined with a commercially available resin system to manufacture a fibre reinforced polymer matrix composite.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Following this introduction, the materials and testing regime are outlined and this is followed by results from tensile testing. This is broken down into two parts:

firstly quasi-static results are considered followed by a study of strain recovery. The paper concludes with some thoughts on the relevance of this class of material to engineering applications.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

2.2.1 Viscose Rayon Fibre

The fibre used in the current study, Cordenka 700 (Cordenka GmbH) is viscose rayon fibre of similar dimensions to E-glass (diameter of ~ 15 μm) and is available commercially in a continuous form.

As viscose rayon is a cellulosic fibre, it was expected that this fibre would adsorb moisture, in a similar manner to natural fibres, when stored under laboratory conditions. Therefore, before any lamination of the viscose rayon fibre, a residual moisture experiment was conducted to check what duration of drying was required before lamination, as previously used for natural fibres [26].

After 5 hours of drying at 105 °C it was found that viscose rayon experienced a mass loss of around 11 %. The moisture content of the viscose rayon was around 25% greater than for the other natural fibres investigated previously, but this is not entirely surprising given the reformed nature of the cellulosic structure. Similar to the natural fibres, the rate of moisture loss within the viscose rayon fibre decreased significantly after the two hour mark and so it was determined that two hours of fibre drying would be sufficient prior to laminating.

2.2.2 Polymer resin matrix

As the standard resin systems available from Scott Bader are specifically tailored for conventional reinforcements, the highest elongation at break for a closed mould resin system is around 6 % strain. This is suitable for conventional reinforcements which all have a strain to fracture of half this value. The Cordenka 700 series yarn has a strain at break of 12 – 14% and hence if a unidirectional or cross-ply viscose rayon composite was made with a standard resin, this resin would fail much earlier than the fibre. Many of the commercial resin systems at Scott Bader are blends of different base resins. Scott Bader manufactures two high elongation base resins, one is an unsaturated polyester (UP) type resin and the other is urethane methacrylate (UMa) type resin. By blending a conventional resin system, in this case Crestapol 1212, with other high elongation base resins it was possible to create resin systems with a higher elongation at break whilst retaining acceptable stiffness and strength.

The properties of these blended resins were unknown. As a result, the mechanical properties at 60:40, 50:50 and 40:60 blends of the two possible combinations were investigated and the optimum ratio was found to be 50:50 in both cases.

Previous experience of natural fibres has shown the necessity of the use of a coupling agent to improve the interfacial adhesion of natural fibre reinforced composites [24]. From understanding how a coupling agent is designed for a synthetic fibre, a proprietary unsaturated oligomer was investigated as a coupling agent to promote interface adhesion between the natural fibre and the thermosetting resin system. This coupling agent has two functional groups: one functional group will form a chemical bond with the –OH groups on the surface of a natural fibre whilst the other functional group is unsaturated to enable cross-linking with the polymer matrix. As natural fibres are sensitive to moisture, this coupling agent was designed specifically so that it would not develop water from the reaction with the surface of the natural fibre. The coupling agent was then added to the blended resin systems at 10 wt.%.

2.3 Manufacturing

For the viscose rayon yarn to be used within a composite, the fibres were wound around a square steel frame. The external area of the frame was 420 mm x 420 mm. The sides of the frame were made from 25 mm wide and 4 mm thick mild steel. As a unidirectional composite was required, the fibre was wound in one plane. The final composite needed to have a 3 mm thickness in order for these viscose

rayon laminates to have similar thicknesses to the other composites. This thickness was governed by the amount of fibre applied to the frame.

Initial testing showed that the untwisted/uncoated yarn, of the available forms of Cordenka 700, gave the best mechanical properties and this was used for the planned test regime. After the initial round of testing, it was noticed that the rayon fibres contract during drying, resulting in a buckled frame. This buckled frame hindered the VARTM process, leading to splitting of the vacuum bag. In order to reduce the tendency for this buckling, a removable spacer was added to the frame during winding and was removed prior to the fibre drying process. It was later determined that the viscose rayon frames could not be infused with the VARTM process as the compression force applied to the fibres by the vacuum bag restricted the flow of resin. The first attempt to solve this problem was to pour the catalysed resin on top of the fibre within the mould before the vacuum bag was applied, but air became trapped in the system, resulting in porosity within the cured laminate. Despite these manufacturing faults, preliminary testing showed that the viscose rayon composites demonstrated potential for good mechanical properties. Hence, a purpose built infusion mould was made which led to laminates of improved quality being produced.

All of the resins used in the current study are room temperature cure systems. Following cure at room temperature for 24 hours in the mould, all resin plaques and composite laminates were de-moulded and post-cured in an oven at 40 °C for 16 hours. After post-curing, specimens were cut for testing. The laminate thicknesses are presented in Table 1, together with fibre volume fractions, which were calculated using the Archimedes buoyancy calculation.

Table 1. Thickness of unidirectional laminates with viscose rayon fibres

Composite Type	Specimen Thickness (mm)	Fibre Volume Fraction
Un-dried 1212	3.1	0.56
1212	4.8	0.43
1212/UMa2	3.7	0.48
1212/UP2	3.3	0.54
1212/CA	3.7	0.46
1212/UMa2/CA	3.8	0.49
1212/UP2/CA	3.5	0.50

2.4 Mechanical Testing

Coupons were cut to 25 mm by 200 mm. To give a test length of 150 mm, end tabs of a $\pm 45^\circ$ woven E-glass polyester composite cut to 25 mm by 25 mm were used. Five specimens from each laminate were tested in the 0° fibre direction (BS EN ISO 527 – Part 5: 1997) using an Instron quasi-static test machine (3382) with a 50 kN load cell. The test displacement rate was 2 mm min⁻¹. The rate of testing was selected so that the specimen extended at around 1 % per minute. This meant that specimens were tested in accordance with BS EN ISO 527 – Part 1: 1996. The stiffness of each material was determined from the initial elastic region and the peak tensile strength and the strain at break recorded. The strain was measured using an extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Tensile Testing

Results from tensile testing of these laminates are presented in **Figures 1** (Young's modulus), **2** (peak tensile strength) and **3** (strain at failure). Comparisons within this section assume that the fibre volume fractions are similar for all laminates.

From looking firstly at the blended systems (with and without coupling agent), there was no significant effect of resin type on the composite tensile stiffness and strength. There was a slight reduction in the tensile strain at failure of the 1212/UP through the addition of the coupling agent but no noticeable change with the 1212/UMa system.

Figure 1 - Young's modulus of viscose rayon composites utilising different resin systems

Figure 2 - Tensile strength of viscose rayon composites utilising different resin systems

Figure 3 - Tensile strain at failure of viscose rayon composites utilising different resin systems

The 1212 laminate showed the lowest tensile stiffness, strength and strain at failure. When the coupling agent was used (1212/CA) there was a notable increase in strain at failure. Previously it has been shown that the use of the coupling agent decreased the strain at failure of the hemp composite [24] and it was expected that this VR laminate would have a lower strain at failure. As these viscose rayon fibres were expected to have far lower defects/dislocations than the natural fibres, one possibility was that the load transfer capability had improved such that the composite was more resilient to fracture at lower stresses.

It was interesting that the un-dried fibre laminate with the 1212 resin showed a higher than average tensile stiffness but a lower than average tensile strength. As the resin with un-dried hemp fibre had previously been shown to achieve poor composite properties, the higher moisture content of viscose rayon (compared with the other natural fibres) was expected to reduce the composite properties further. A possible explanation of this observed result was that the viscose rayon fibre is continuous in length with no defects, unlike natural fibres that are short and have dislocations. This meant that lower interface strength was not a concern using this test procedure with this type of fibre.

From the results presented, it can be seen that the 1212/UP blends (with and without coupling agent) achieved the highest stiffness and strength compared to the other resin systems.

As the results in **Table 1** demonstrate that there were variations of laminate thickness across the different laminate configurations, this will have had an effect on the fibre volume fraction of those composites. As a result, the (fibre-dominated) tensile results could have been distorted. Using the fibre volume fractions of each laminate, it is possible to normalise the tensile results to a fibre volume fraction of 0.5 (see figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4 - Normalised Young's modulus of viscose rayon composites utilising different resin systems (normalised to $0.5 V_f$)

Figure 5 - Normalised tensile strength of viscose rayon composites utilising different resin systems (normalised to $0.5 V_f$)

These normalised data show that the un-dried fibre composite has the lowest stiffness and strength compared with the other composite systems. There were also no noticeable differences between the 1212/UMa2 and 1212/UP2 composites. When the coupling agent was added to the base resin (1212/CA), there was a 12 % increase in tensile strength with no change in Young's modulus. The addition of the coupling agent to the 1212/UMa2 led to a slight decrease in the tensile stiffness and strength, whereas the coupling agent added to the 1212/UP2 resulted in a slight increase in stiffness and strength. The composite that achieved the highest stiffness and strength was the composite with the 1212/UP2/CA resin system.

3.2 Non-Linearity and Strain Recovery

Single fibre tension tests within the published literature have demonstrated that regenerated cellulose fibres exhibit non-linear elastic properties [27]. Therefore, it was expected that the composite would show similar tensile stress-strain behaviour that was reported within the research of single fibre tests.

To test this hypothesis and determine the resulting composite mechanical properties, a cyclic tensile test was carried out. Three composite coupons were loaded to either 3 %, 4.5 % or 6 % strain, then subsequently unloaded, rested for 24 hours and then reloaded to fracture. The stress-strain graphs from the 3 %, 4.5 % and 6 % initial strain loading can be seen in **Figures 6 to 8** respectively. The strain recovery over time for all of the specimens can be seen in **Figure 9**.

When the specimens were loaded, there was a high initial stiffness (~ 13 GPa) which then decreased to a lower stiffness (~ 3.3 GPa) at a stress above 100 MPa. These lower stiffnesses were relatively constant up to the limit of initial loading (3%, 4.5% or 6% strain). When the specimens were unloaded, there was a high stiffness which constantly decreased till the specimens were unloaded fully. The initial and final stiffnesses were dependent on the pre-strain (14 GPa to 6.5 GPa for 3 % pre-strain and 16 GPa to 3 GPa for 4.5 % pre-strain). During the rest phase, the strains decreased over time ($\sim 1.2\%$ for each specimen), and were reasonably linear on a log plot (Figure 9), illustrating some form of recovery. When the specimens were reloaded, there was still an initial high stiffness, which was similar to the initial loading that also decreased to a lower stiffness at a stress above 100 MPa. Depending on the amount of pre-straining, the reduced stiffness for each re-loaded specimen was such that the stress at the pre-strain limit was identical to the stress observed for the reloaded specimen at that same strain (3.8 GPa for 3 %, 4.7 GPa for 4.5 % and 5.5 GPa for 6 % pre-strained specimens). Once the specimens were loaded past the pre-strain limit, the stiffness decreased and was linear up to fracture. This observable difference between specimens indicates that the pre-strain created a different strain rate dependent/recovery component within the elastic-plastic behaviour shown by this fibre.

Figure 6 Stress-strain graph of VR composite coupon specimen loaded to 3 % strain¹

¹ Owing to a power failure, this specimen test was interrupted during the relaxation stage. As there were no more specimens to test, this specimen was allowed to recover over 15 days before it was completely re-tested. As such, both of the initial loading and un-loading responses before and after power failure are presented to show the validity of re-test

Figure 7 - Stress-strain graph of VR composite coupon specimen loaded to 4.5 % strain

Figure 8 - Stress-strain graph of VR composite coupon specimen loaded to 6 % strain

Figure 9 - Strain recovery for specimens 1, 2 and 3 (3 %, 4.5 % and 6 % strain respectively; zero load over 24 hours)

It seems that the stiffness of the elastic region was similar before and after pre-strain, independent of the amount of pre-strain applied. The stiffness within the non-elastic region was relatively linear before and after pre-strain. Once the re-loading strain had reached the initial pre-strain, the stiffness slightly decreased until failure. The amount of strain rate recovery was also independent of the pre-strain of the specimen.

These data have interesting implications for both energy absorption applications and for some level of recovery after impact.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Ever greater demands are being made of materials, with sundry additional properties required in addition to good mechanical performance. The green credentials of materials are beginning to become an important parameter, although there is some difficulty in achieving consensus on exactly what this means. The current work has shown that viscose rayon, a bio-derived material that can be fibreised can be used with commercial resin systems to produce laminates with potentially useful mechanical properties. Whilst the stiffness of composites made from these fibres is comparatively low, the composites do show some recovery over time, which is an interesting area for further study. With the developments in the processing of biomass (both primary sources and waste/byproduct from other activity) to extract cellulose and other macromolecules, and in turn the conversion of this into a range of fibres including cellulosic and lignin based precursors for carbon fibres, it must be remembered that every extra process requires an input of energy. On this basis, it is worth looking at simpler fibres which are 'good enough'. On this basis, viscose rayon and other cellulosic fibres have the potential to be used in a range of engineering applications.

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